

Look Good, Feel Good, Play Good: How Division I Athletes Negotiate Gendered Expectations
in Women's Sports

by

Madeline L. Phantumabamrung

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Approved by:

Carrie M. Lane

Dr. Carrie Lane, Department of American Studies

Stacy Mallicoat

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

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Abstract

Historically, sports have been one of the most dominant mediums through which masculinity has been demonstrated and reinforced in American culture. The strength, speed, skill, aggression, body type, and, in some cases, violence that is often required to succeed in competitive sports has been essentialized as masculine. This leaves athletes in women's sports to negotiate perceptions and pressures surrounding expectations of both their femininity and their performance as athletes. In order to better understand these social realities, Phantumabamrung interviewed ten student athletes from a range of women's sports at California State University Fullerton. Due to the different lived experiences that individuals have depending on racial, sexual, and gender identities, diversity of the sample was of high importance. Drawing from the athletes' experiences in soccer, softball, cross country, track and field, and waterpolo, patterns began to emerge involving confidence, empowerment, body image, and struggle. These patterns have important implications for many different research fields including kinesiology, psychology, sociology, and women and gender studies.

Keywords: women, sports, athletics, expectation, feminine, masculine

Introduction

In March of 2021, the NCAA Women's March Madness Tournament gained attention for the disparities in weight rooms provided for the men's and women's teams in the COVID-19 bubble. Ali Kershner, the Stanford sports performance coach, posted side-by-side pictures of the men's weight room, complete with racks, barbells, benches, and an extensive set of dumbbells, and the women's set-up, which included only yoga mats and twelve dumbbells (Yücel, 2021). The post later went viral and was reposted by large platforms covering women's sports, which then prompted a response from the NCAA in which they cited lack of space as the most pressing reason for the inequality (NCAA March Madness, 2021). The then University of Oregon forward, Sedona Prince, posted a TikTok video disproving the claim that there was not enough space in the women's bubble, and once again calling the NCAA out on their discriminatory facilities and asking for better (Yücel, 2021). Her caption stated, "it's 2021 and we are still fighting for bits and pieces of equality" (Prince, 2021). Not only were the different facilities evidence of the disparities in treatment and funding, but they also spoke to gendered expectations of college athletes. The dumbbells present in the women's set-up were so light that they only ever could have been capable of toning. Never strengthening or bulking. They might have served an aesthetic purpose, but were deficient in their ability to increase or sustain Division I athletic performance.

Three years later, the 2024 women's March Madness tournament received unprecedented attention from fans. For the first time, the women's tournament seemed to be surrounded by more enthusiasm than the men's tournament, with NBA players like LeBron James referring to the women driving viewership in the college game – Angel Reese, JuJu Watkins, Caitlin Clark, Paige Bueckers, and Cameron Brink – as "icons" who create "legacies" at their programs

(McMenamin, 2024). Unprecedented progress has been made in terms of recognition and attention earned by women's basketball over the last ten years, and yet there is still evidence of the ways in which women remain bound by gendered expectations. Throughout the tournament viewers saw the women chastised online for their aggressive styles of play and communication during games, while this same behavior goes unquestioned when exhibited by male athletes (Darvin, 2024). At the same time, there were countless examples of athletes sporting elaborate hair extensions, eyelash extensions, and in some cases makeup during games.

This year's tournament came to a head with Iowa and South Carolina facing off in the final. After South Carolina secured the victory, forward Chloe Kitts rushed to put earrings on while she was on the bench, in preparation for the championship pictures that would be taken after the game. Women watching around the country exclaimed how relatable this was on social media. Commenters wrote things like "the girls that get it, get it," "girls being GIRLS as they SHOULD even when playing a male dominated sport," and "this is girlhood" (espnW, 2024). The intentionality that it took for Kitts to keep her earrings on the bench in case pictures would be taken afterwards speaks to the pressure that many athletes who compete in women's sports feel to meet certain standards of femininity.

Sports often function as a microcosm of the culture in which they are situated. In the United States, a country in which capitalism and patriarchy inform all aspects of life, the sports industry is largely fueled by profit margins and occupied by men. Sports have historically been one of the most dominant mediums through which hegemonic masculinity has been solidified and internalized in American culture. The roughness, strength, speed, skill, and aggression that is required to succeed in competitive sports serves as an affirmation of one's status as man: proof of an excellent performance of masculinity. However, the same can not be said for women, who

have struggled against narratives that kept them out of sports. Throughout history, wealthy, white women have been thought of as sensitive, delicate, gentle, and beautiful: all traits that do not seem to fit conveniently into the male-dominated world of competitive sports. Women of color were usually not associated with these “feminine” characteristics, yet they were still restricted from participation in sports on the basis of both sex and race. The very act of participating in sports as a woman can be understood as subversive, going against the grain of traditional femininity and challenging the monopoly that men have claimed on the domain. This positions athletes competing in women’s sports in a unique position, forcing them to negotiate their athleticism, gender expression, sexuality, and social standing. There are themes within this negotiation, but ultimately the experience of each person is distinct, subject to differences in race, class, sexual orientation, gender expression, ability, passions, etc.

Literature Review

Sports as a Male Domain

In the late 1800s and early 1900s, inaccurate scientific theories, medical practices, and beliefs reaffirmed sexist depictions of women as the physiologically inferior sex whose bodies were thought to be weakened by reproduction. In her book, *Coming on Strong: Gender and Sexuality in Women’s Sport*, Susan Cahn writes about the ways these practices and beliefs not only served to keep women out of public life, but also strategically painted women’s bodies as unfit for sports. Instead, “sport had developed as a male preserve, a domain in which men expressed and cultivated masculinity throughout athletic competition” while the “tension between sport and femininity” led to many obstacles for women looking to enter into the world of competitive sports (Cahn, 2015). She writes that this was exemplified in the 1890s when the cycling craze that swept across the United States opened up new opportunities for women

looking to affirm their right to public exercise outdoors; this opportunity was only available to women within the economic elite. Critics of this phenomena argued that bicycling had the potential to cause intense physiological damage, especially with regard to reproductive capabilities and aesthetic qualities. In this way, both physiological and physical misunderstandings of women's abilities were weaponized as tools to ensure that male ownership of sports remained as unchallenged as possible.

This ideology of male ownership and superiority has been a nagging theme throughout the history of sports in America. Samantha Sheppard explores this in her book, *Sporting Blackness: Race, Embodiment, and Critical Muscle Memory on Screen*, through her discussion of the All-American Girls Baseball League (AAGBL). The AAGBL functioned from 1943 through 1954 and was created by Philip Wrigley during World War II as a "wartime surrogate" for men's professional baseball (Sheppard, 2020). In other words, there was only a drive to create a (white) women's league during the absence of male players. The women were not there because they were finally being recognized as equal competitors. They were there to fill an economic void and were pushed out of the space as soon as the men returned from war. In addition, the women were forced to observe strict rules of conduct to navigate and maintain the "cultural dissonance between 'masculine' athleticism and 'feminine' womanhood" (Sheppard, 2020). Sheppard writes that these rules included directives like always wearing feminine attire when not playing and keeping their hair long. These rules served as a representation of the restricted privilege that was available to white women at the time, as well as the double burden that Black women faced as a result of both racial and gender discrimination. Not only did the AAGBL ultimately reinforce the idea that sports are a male domain, but it also affirmed that Black women have been held to completely different standards and expectations of womanhood.

Unfortunately, these historical truths are not without present day consequences and parallels. The sporting industry and culture were irrevocably changed by the exclusion of Black women in the formative years of its inception.

Unfortunately, the pattern by which social ideas about femininity inform scientific study has continued into present day practice. Most recently, gender verification tests have been used to police the bodies of athletes competing in women's sports. Vanessa Heggie writes about the history and implications of gender verification tests for women in sports in her article *Testing Sex and Gender in Sports: Reinventing, Reimagining, and Reconstructing Histories*. Gender verification tests were first introduced in the international sporting world in the 1960's in response to paranoia over "gender fraud," which largely came from fascist and communist regimes (Heggie, 2010). Suspicions of fraud were largely built upon stereotypes. Women who were extremely muscular and had deeper voices were often targeted. Testing involves a series of different protocols that effectively "provide an upper limit for women's sporting performance; there is a point at which your masculine-style body is declared 'too masculine,' and you are disqualified, regardless of your personal gender identity" (Heggie, 2010). Yet, there is no physiological limit against which men are judged. Women who are excellent at their sports, invite investigation into the physiological makeup of their bodies, while men who are excellent at their sports are accepted free of question. Unfortunately, these tests have had a disproportionately negative effect on women of color, such as Caster Semenya and Dutee Chand, runners who have had their careers completely disrupted by binary standards enforced by gender verification tests.

Title IX

American women's sports were changed forever on June 23, 1972 with the passage of Title IX of the Education Amendments of 1972. Katie Barnes writes about the thirty-seven word law that banned sex-discrimination in education, and all of its attachments, most notably including sports, in their book *Fair Play: How Sports Shape the Gender Debates*. They argue that without Title IX, and the funding that it required schools to allot for women's sports, women's sports would essentially be defunct. This is not only evident when looking back at the years prior to 1972, but also clear when considering the professional opportunities available to women in sports today (Barnes, 2023). As of now, the National Women's Soccer League (NWSL) and the Women's National Basketball Association (WNBA) are the only two women's sports leagues that function at a relatively sustainable financial level. Although these leagues are well known in popular culture, the players remain notoriously underpaid. However, in all of the other sports, college remains the premier level of competition in America for women athletes because of the lack of professional opportunities for female players.

Considering the fact that it has been just 52 years since Title IX was signed, and less since it was actually implemented, it is unsurprising that some antiquated narratives about women in sports remain. However, Katie Barnes writes about the ways that certain aspects of Title IX's original intent have been forgotten. At the time of its passage, large questions pertaining to the implementation of Title IX remained unanswered. They write that the thirty-seven words present on the bill did not explain whether or not "nondiscrimination and equal opportunity" meant increasingly implementing women into the existing system or creating a different system that would be separate and equal (2023). Many interest groups were worried that the separate but equal system would result in a "glass ceiling effect," but women at the time were unpracticed and believed to be unready to enter into male sports teams who had been

practicing for years (Barnes, 2023). If gender integration would have happened in the 1970s, women likely would have been pushed out of sports before they had ever gotten the opportunity to practice and earn a position. As a result, the National Organization for Women (NOW) ultimately supported sex segregation in sports as a means to a more equal end (Barnes, 2023). The ultimate goal of gender integration seems to have largely been forgotten, and as feared, women's competitive sports are generally not seen as holding equal value in the athletic space.

Sexualization & Consumption of Women's Bodies in Sport

As women continue to push boundaries and break records in sports, American culture has a pattern of cutting them back down to size by reducing them to sexual objects. In her book *Throw Like a Girl, Cheer Like a Boy: The Evolution of Gender, Identity, and Race in Sports*, Robyn Ryle writes about how people in the early 20th century were extremely concerned about the ways that sports would make women "mannish" and foster an "unnatural female masculinity" (2020). In the 1920s, sports organizers and promoters began combatting the notion of "mannishness" by emphasizing the femininity and sexual attractiveness of female athletes and attaching "feminine" competitions to sporting events (Cahn, 2015; Ryle, 2020). The attached competitions often came in the forms of musical contests, post-game dances, and even beauty pageants (Ryle, 2020). Ultimately, these performances were more for the purpose of reaffirming a feminine gender expression than for a show of talent. They served to take agency away from the female athlete and remind her (and others) that she is only ever as good as she is attractive to men. Cahn summarizes this by writing that "although the popular athlete might display "masculine" athletic ability, she establishes her femininity through her attractiveness to men" (Cahn, 2015).

This pattern was again reaffirmed when the US Women's National Soccer Team won the 1999 World Cup and Brandi Chastain tore off her shirt after scoring the winning penalty kick. Jamie Schultz writes about this iconic moment in sports history in her book *Qualifying Times: Points of Change in U.S. Women's Sports*, recalling how the match between the United States and China had gone on for a full 120 minutes without a single goal. They were tied in the shootout, 4-4, leaving the pressure of the title on Chastain's shoulders. Yet after scoring the goal, helping to bring home the World Cup Title for her country, and accomplishing a massive athletic feat in playing the over-time in addition to the regulation 90 minutes, the media had a frenzy over her celebration: more specifically her sports bra (2014). Since then, Chastain published a book appropriately titled "It's Not About the Sports Bra." However, Shultz argues that in the cultural context of the day it was all about the sports bra because the attention that Chastain's celebration received effectively "reduced one of the most significant moments in sport history to one that gave the world 'that girl in the sports bra'" (2014).

There is an even more extensive history of Black women's bodies being disrespected and oversexualized, and it has roots back in the colonial period. Robyn Ryle uses Serena Williams's catsuit as an example of the ways that discussion about Black women's clothes and bodies can be used to discredit and distract from their athletic accomplishments. In 2018, after giving birth to her first child, Serena Williams returned to tennis in Paris, adorned in a skintight black suit that would later come to be known as the catsuit. The media had a frenzy, and it ultimately caused the French Open to enforce a dress code, regardless of the fact that the suit also served a purpose as compression for Williams, who had just suffered blood clots in a traumatic birth experience the year before. However, this was unfortunately not a new experience for her or her sister Venus. Ryle makes it clear that throughout both of their careers, the focus of much of the conversation

surrounding the Williams Sisters has largely been about their race, their hair, their clothes, and their bodies as sexual objects (2020). Ultimately, “the potential empowerment of sports participation is always balanced against the extra burden of sexualization for many Black female athletes” (Ryle, 2020).

The Feminine Apologetic

Although women’s sports have grown in viewership and appreciation within recent decades, female athletes continue to face challenges related to their gender, and are sometimes viewed as a deviation from the feminine norm. In her writing about change in women’s athletics and the women’s movement, Hollis Elkins describes the historical understanding of femininity as the antithesis of athletic capability. She refers to an antiquated definition in which women were seen as physically inactive, uncomfortable in their bodies, and incapable of understanding their own anatomy (Elkins, 1978). This perception, which has loosely been carried on into today, led people in the 1970s to question whether or not the women and girls on the fields were *really* women and girls. Considering that the social environment has undergone much change in the last 50 years, most people would no longer verbalize that thought, but the ideology seems to remain persistent in that female athletes are not always viewed as “normal” girls. “You throw like a girl” is still considered an insult, failing to account for the many girls who play competitive softball and could likely outperform the average boy. The assumption that “normal” girls are weak and that female athletes are the exception to the rule is pervasive and consistent; the “historical” definition that Elkins references has proven difficult to disrupt. However, expanding ideas surrounding gender categories and the movement to supersede the gender binary with a spectrum are further complicating ideas around women’s participation in sports, while challenging traditional understandings of femininity.

This idea of *real* girls not only perpetuates a harmful definition of femininity, but also negatively impacts female athletes, implying that they are less than women. Sylvia Burrow argues that in order to cope with this, many women in athletics have been observed to partake in additional performances of femininity, a behavior described by feminist scholars as the feminine apologetic. The feminine apologetic refers to the efforts that some female athletes make outside of their sport in order to affirm their status as women and counteract the masculine behavior they have exhibited by participating in sports (Burrow, 2016). These efforts include wearing makeup, keeping their hair long, wearing hyper feminine clothing, and downplaying the competitive nature of their sports. It is described as an apology because this rush to return to societal expectations as soon as a woman steps off of the field can be viewed as her apology for violating gender norms while in her place of competition. This behavior once again affirms that the unathletic women are considered feminine, while the women in sports can be “dismissed as an anomaly” (Burrow, 2016).

This urge to “apologize” or maneuver oneself back into the socially prescribed category appears to be a method of self preservation, by which female athletes can avoid many of the harms that come as a result of stigmatization (Burrow, 2016). There is also a sexual component to these behaviors, as heterosexual women can be somewhat afraid of being labeled as lesbians and/or being found unattractive by men. In this way understandings of athletic ability, gender expression, and sexuality are often conflated by observers, leaving women in sports to navigate these complex intersections. The feminine apologetic then exists as a simple “solution” to this problem, affirming one's status as a feminine woman while allowing for the continuation of competition in sports.

Intersectional Analysis

When discussing “women” it is always necessary to specify exactly which women are being referenced. In this case, most prior discussion has been based around the experience of heterosexual female athletes. While many heterosexual women and girls have turned away from competitive sports for fear of being considered gay, many lesbian women and girls were able to see their sports as safe spaces for self-discovery (Adams et al., 2005). Nevertheless, until quite recently, few collegiate and professional female athletes were openly out because they were afraid of losing sponsorships and their fan base (Adams et al., 2005). This seems to be less of a concern in the present day, as many professional and collegiate female athletes are now open about their sexuality and continue to be supported and celebrated for their athletic success.

It is also important to acknowledge that the experience of Black female athletes can be very different from the experience of their white teammates. Many of the academic sources available emphasize the role of surveillance in the life of Black women in collegiate sports. In an ethnographic study on the control and surveillance of Black female student athletes at Midwestern University, Kevin Foster writes about the sacrifice of autonomy and freedom that many of these Black female athletes made in order to be shaped into the highly successful contemporary model of womanhood that faculty wanted them to exemplify. During his time observing the behavior in the athletic department he noticed that staff members continuously treated Black student athletes as if they were immature, academically deficient, and sexually overactive (Foster, 2003).

A similar pattern was found in a study investigating how female body builders negotiate normative femininity. In the course of her interviews, Lex Boyle found that most of her participants reproduced sexist stereotypes of hypermuscular women and “perceived African-American women in the pictures to be more masculine than their white counterparts”

(Boyle, 2005). The intersection of race and gender changes the way that Black female athletes maneuver through the world. This shines light on the need for a diverse selection of interviewees, for this research considering the very different lived experiences that can be found at the intersections of different identity groups.

Methods

In order to gain a better understanding of athletes' experiences in negotiating expectations of femininity with the expectations that they have as Division I athletes, I decided that open-ended interviews would be the optimal methodology. I had considered surveys, but I was worried that surveys would not get me the in-depth understanding that I desired in a way that fully encompassed the reality of this personal experience. I wanted to hear each athlete's thoughts and feelings in a way that was as close to the stream of consciousness as possible, while also being able to ask follow up questions when necessary.

In order to become familiar with the inherently personal experiences that make up the patterns of social behavior and surveillance associated with female athletes, it is necessary to listen and observe. Harry Wolcott describes the benefits and challenges of conducting fieldwork in this manner. By utilizing observed behavior and conversations as data, he states the importance of taking substantial notes, and emphasizes the importance of taking time to synthesize those notes while the information is still fresh because it doesn't make sense to continue gathering information before having digested what has already been obtained (Wolcott 93). Repeatedly, Wolcott warns readers of the ambiguity that is often associated with fieldwork and warns prospective field workers of the need to focus and refocus observations by asking questions as the task seems to grow larger and larger. This type of research often requires the study to be "constructed in the doing" (Wolcott 88).

After deciding to take an ethnographic approach, I went through the process of getting this project approved by the California State University Fullerton Institutional Review Board for research involving human subjects due to the necessary involvement of human participants. Once this was complete, I needed to assemble a group of ten athletes competing in women's sports at CSUF. I did this by drafting an email that could be sent to all the athletes in women's sports at the school. It detailed what this study was about and stressed the importance of a diverse sample of interviewees. A woman in the athletics academic services department sent the email out for me, and I received eight responses.

Most of my initial interviews were with women who had seen the email and volunteered to be a part of the study. However, four of the athletes who had originally responded, did not reply when reached back out to. For this reason, snowball sampling was used to reach the desired number of ten participants. Some of these additional athletes were selected based on recommendations from people that I had already interviewed and others were selected in order to ensure the diversity of the experiences represented within the research. For example, although racially diverse, most of the initial respondents were cisgender, heterosexual women who played soccer. I had to ask around in order to find athletes who were from a wider range of sports and had different gender identities and sexual orientations. I was given the numbers of two different people to contact, and neither of them ever responded. As a result, I reached out to people I personally knew that I thought would be willing to help me diversify my sample. Each participant filled out a short questionnaire listing their racial identity, sexual orientation, and preferred pronouns prior to the start of their interview.

The interviews themselves were mostly conducted on campus, and at nearby coffee shops. They ranged from twenty to fifty minutes long, but averaged around thirty minutes on

average. Considering the fact that my main goal was to understand the experiences of the people sitting in front of me, some of the dialogue was made up of conversation stems so as not to limit the responses, or lead them in any way. For example, “tell me about your experience as a Division I athlete,” was intended to get the athletes comfortable and to see what they thought was most important to share, without any leading towards a gendered analysis of their experience. Once I had a general understanding of their experiences and they had warmed into the conversation, I would begin asking more structured questions like “have you ever felt like competing in sports at a high level made people perceive you as masculine?” and “how do you feel about wearing makeup while you compete?” These conversation stems and questions came from a list of twenty that I used as a structural framework for my interviews. At times, certain questions were skipped if the interviewee felt like they had already answered, and at other times, I asked additional follow up questions to get a more detailed explanation where I felt it was necessary.

After the interviews were completed, I transcribed them using Otter.ai. I then went back through each recording and corrected the transcripts. Once that process was complete, I printed all ten of them out and annotated the copies so that I could start to mark the themes I had already heard, and potentially recognize new ones.

Participants

Participant 1 is a multiracial (Black/white) cisgender, heterosexual woman who is on the women’s soccer team. She uses she/her pronouns.

Participant 2 is a multiracial (white/Hispanic) cisgender, heterosexual woman who also competes on the women’s soccer team. She uses she/her pronouns.

Participant 3 is a white cisgender, heterosexual woman who plays on the softball team. She is most comfortable with she/her pronouns.

Participant 4 is a Hispanic cisgender, heterosexual woman who is on the track and field team. More specifically, she is a thrower. She uses she/her pronouns.

Participant 5 is a Latin American cisgender, heterosexual woman who competes on the women's water polo team. She prefers she/her pronouns.

Participant 6 is a multiracial (African American/Hispanic/white) cisgender, heterosexual woman who competes on the track and field team. More specifically, she is a hurdler. Her pronouns are she/her.

Participant 7 is a multiracial (Danish/Mexican) queer athlete who plays on the women's soccer team. Their pronouns are he/they.

Participant 8 is a multiracial (white/Guamanian) cisgender, bisexual woman who competes on the women's soccer team. Her pronouns are she/her.

Participant 9 is a white cisgender, heterosexual woman who is on the cross country and track and field teams. She uses she/her pronouns.

Participant 10 is a white cisgender, bisexual woman who plays on the softball team. However, it is notable that college was her first experience with softball because she grew up playing baseball with boys. Her preferred pronouns are she/her.

Findings and Analysis

Throughout the course of the ten interviews, five notable themes began to show up reliably. First, every single interviewee spoke of the ways in which playing sports has increased their confidence. However, this confidence was often in contention with the insecurities that can run rampant among athletes in women's sports, especially regarding expectations of "feminine"

body types that are usually not built for sports. Relatedly, most of the athletes interviewed talked about wearing light makeup while they compete because it is a part of their pre-game routine. This behavior, along with others mentioned throughout the interviews can be understood through the lens of the feminine apologetic: compensation for the ways in which participating in sports paints them in a masculine light. Lastly, all interviewees demonstrated a strong sense of self and internal fluidity between their gender identities and their position as a Division I athlete. They were at peace with the ways that different sides of themselves come together to make up their personhood, yet they expressed that when they do experience tension between identities (especially those related to athleticism and gender) they come from an external source.

Confidence

Sports have the potential to be incredibly liberatory and empowering for athletes all over the world, but this power is even more evident for athletes occupying women's spaces. Throughout the interviews, it became apparent that the experience of competing in Division I sports actually has the ability to change a person and alter the way they show up in the world for the better. Participant 2 spoke about this, having repeatedly expressed the ways that her experience as an athlete increased her confidence. She added that college athletics have "made [her] mentally stronger, and made [her] really believe in [herself] more," as well as having "definitely made [her] more confident, strong headed, and aggressive." This growth came as a result of knowing that "[she] earned this," because nothing comes easy in sports. Similarly, Participant 1 talked a lot about how sports have increased her self-confidence because "you're constantly putting in work," which can foster a sense of pride and self-worth. This confidence comes as a natural result of facing large challenges and working to overcome them, something

that is an everyday task for division one athletes. In many ways, spending years honing a skill and growing confidence can be liberating to athletes competing in women's sports.

Insecurity

However, many remain affected by insecurities that usually revolve around image. On this topic, Participant 4 stated that “if our muscles are too big then it's like oh, you look like a man and you're trying too hard,” but “then if our muscles aren't big enough, it's like ok you're not going to be good because you're not athletic and you're not muscular.” She even went on to describe the fact that sometimes she is tempted to lift less weight because she doesn't want to look manly or draw attention that would cause people to make comments, saying “[her] shoulders are bigger than most guys, so sometimes it makes [her] not want to try as hard.”

Participant 4 briefly summarized her experience of conflict, explaining that “if [she] weren't an athlete, [she] wouldn't have a lot of the femininity issues [she has] now. [She] would not think [she looks] like a man, [she] would not have problems like [she] wouldn't have body image issues. It's like you're constantly proving yourself and you're never going to be enough.” This is effectively showing the ways in which the confidence that can be created through athletic competition for women is also tied up in a nuanced relationship with insecurity. Succeeding in one area can feel like failing in the other.

This relationship between confidence and insecurity was also felt by Participant 7, but it looked different as a result of their nonbinary identity and life experience. They talked a lot in our interview about the challenge of opening up, considering the fact that they haven't completely come out to their team yet. This is a result of the fact that they are scared to make their teammates feel uncomfortable, yet they “already feel like [they] make them uncomfortable being a queer person.” In many ways, Participant 7 wants to be seen as more masculine and

appreciates the ways that sports have helped them do this, yet at the same time they are insecure about the way that they are being perceived by the women that they are surrounded by. They have wrestled with the fact that “being on a women’s team is kind of blocking [them] from being [their] full self in ways” because they really don’t identify as a woman and it can get really uncomfortable to have to explain to people.

Although the experiences of these two athletes are similar in the sense that athletics can simultaneously foster confidence and insecurity, they are also very different. The female athlete feels empowered by her agency and hindered by a constant pressure to look a certain way, to be attractive to men, to be “smaller.” The non-binary athlete’s confidence is two-fold in that they experience agency and a confirmation of the masculine gender they are expressing. They do not feel an overwhelming pressure to assimilate to the feminine standard or to be perceived in a way that makes them “attractive” to others. Instead, their insecurity comes from the fear that living authentically might cause their friends to be uncomfortable. In essence, sports help Participant 7 boost their masculine gender expression, but the fact that they compete in a division entitled “women’s sports” is a hindrance to that boost.

It is also important to note that the type of sport likely has a direct impact on the experience of bodily insecurity. Athletes that compete in soccer, softball, waterpolo, and certain events in track and field spoke of feeling this tension between societal expectations of a feminine body and the body types that their sports require. However, female participants in other events in track and field (those more geared towards running) did not seem to share this experience. In fact, Participant 6 explicitly stated that “[she doesn’t] have any insecurities about [her] build or anything like that.” Participant 9 never brought up having any feelings of insecurity about her body either. This is likely due to the ways in which violence, and relatedly sports that involve

physical contact, have been coded as masculine, which then creates unique muscle structures that are also considered masculine.

Makeup

Of the ten athletes that were interviewed, only seven of them wear makeup in their day-to-day lives. Of the seven that do wear makeup, six prefer to wear light makeup (mostly an emphasis on mascara) during competition. Participant 5 is the only one that does not, and she stated that this is due to the fact that makeup in the pool is just not a feasible or functional option due to the fact that it would likely run and obscure her vision. The six that do wear makeup all had similar explanations. Participant 8 said that she wears it because “look good, feel good, play good basically,” but also “it’s just part of the routine for everyone in the locker room, like [the women on the soccer team] all go to the bathroom and look in the mirror and put on some makeup and everyone feels nice.” Participant 9 repeated the same “look good, feel good, play good” sentiment and added that “it’s like race day, or like track day, is a little pageant over here; you wear a full face of makeup and do your hair in fancy ways.” Interestingly, she mentioned that prior to college she never wore makeup for races. When asked what caused her change of heart, she said that “it was just communal like everyone was here and doing it and I was like I’m not going to show up on the line looking like crap.” Similarly, Participant 1 noted that she saw pictures that the photographers had taken during the games and liked the way her eyes looked better in the ones where she was wearing mascara. These experiences make a large case for the impact of socialization on the use of makeup and the importance of image in women’s sports.

Feminine Apologetic

Wearing makeup in and out of a competitive setting can be considered a part of the feminine apologetic. However, apologetic behavior can also manifest itself in many other ways.

It can be seen in the form of hyper-feminine clothing, long hair, alterations to one's face or body, and mannerisms. Participant 5 spoke on this: “[water polo players] don’t look beautiful while playing, we’re just playing, which sucks because sometimes we don’t feel beautiful, but that’s not really the point.” She has noticed that “[water polo players] put [their] hair down right away after getting out of the pool because [they] joke: dang are [observers] going to know if we are guys or girls?” Here, she has made it clear external messaging has convinced her it is impossible for her and her teammates to be beautiful while they compete. Not only does this bring the shallow and stringent nature of society’s ideal “beauty” to light, but it also offers a perspective into the complicated feelings of women who have been conditioned to believe that being beautiful is their most important task. A lesson that impacts them in all areas of life, even as they know their focus should be solely tied to their game, not how they look during competition. Relatedly, Participant 3 states that she “literally hates dresses... but if [she] doesn’t ever wear a skirt, [she doesn’t] think [she’ll] ever get a boyfriend because the sports thing is already going against [her].” Once again, this illustrates the pervasiveness of the feeling that participation in competitive sports is seen as a detractor from a woman’s femininity that must be counteracted through apologetic behaviors.

The feminine apologetic is not only evident in behaviors, but it can also be seen internally. For example, several athletes discussed questioning themselves and feeling like they should maybe behave more femininely at times. Participant 10 described an experience in which she asked herself “am I not feminine enough for people to think that I’m a woman? But then it’s like at the same time it’s like I don’t really care.” Here, it is evident that the feminine apologetic even affects those who consciously choose not to act on it, adding an additional mental and emotional load.

It is helpful to think about the feminine apologetic and the many behaviors that fall under it through the lens of Foucault's notion of biopower as well as his theory of surveillance under the panopticon. For Foucault, biopower is a medium by which to control people in large groups. One means of achieving biopower is through the panopticon, an architectural structure that essentially would allow guards to see into individual cells without the inmates being able to see out. The inmates cannot tell whether or not they are being watched at all times. Under the illusion of constant surveillance, inmates begin to act as if they are constantly being watched and judged. In essence, true power is teaching individuals to police themselves. This is incredibly helpful to think about as a social construct because whether or not all men are actually viewing athletes competing in women's sports as masculine, and consequently less attractive, that ideology has become so pervasive that it pushes female athletes to police themselves so as to avoid being "caught" being perceived as masculine.

Internal Fluidity and External Tension

All four of the previous themes— confidence, insecurity, makeup, and the feminine apologetic — culminate in the final pattern: all ten of the athletes interviewed possess a sense of internal fluidity with their identities and a sense of external tension. Participant 6 beautifully summarized this experience: "as an athlete and as a woman, I see myself as a strong, independent woman, who's self-motivated and hardworking... they're one in the same, but sometimes I just look and I'll be like okay, I'm a girl, should I be acting more like this?" Without the noise — critical comments, unrealistic depictions in media, and underrepresentation in sports discourse — from the outside world, the cisgender athletes who were interviewed feel perfectly comfortable as women in sports; they are unable to separate their experiences as athletes from their experiences as women, and vice versa. The nonbinary athlete feels perfectly comfortable with

their gender identity, gender expression, and their experience as an athlete. They are the same person they have always been. However, outside voices and expectations put pressure on that internal fluidity resulting in a constant state of tension. Tension between who they really are and who the world expects them to be. In a lot of ways, sport – in its most raw form, stripped of all of the social agendas – is a more beautiful version of that story, in which the athlete exists in a constant state of tension between who they currently are and who they are pushing themselves to be. Sport involves physical and mental tension, but for athletes competing in women’s sports, sport is also a space of social tension, a gendered tension.

Future Considerations

This research does not yet include consideration of sports that are traditionally considered more feminine: dance, cheer, gymnastics, figure-skating, etc. It also does not include a dedicated focus on sports that do not involve physical contact: golf, tennis, swimming, diving, etc. Future research should investigate the ways in which these sports could potentially change this discourse, and consider the gendered standards by which activities are or aren’t labeled as “sports.” Additionally, there is a related opportunity to investigate the ways in which different populations of men actually view athletes who compete in women’s sports. The current research is focused on women’s experiences, which naturally includes their perceptions and assumptions about men’s thoughts. It would be interesting, and potentially beneficial, to view this topic from a different perspective.

Conclusion

Throughout American history, sports have shown themselves to be a positive force for social change and a stage on which cultural values are made evident. Through these ten interviews with athletes competing in women’s sports at California State University Fullerton, it

is clear that sports have the capacity to generate confidence and mental fortitude in girls and women, as well as a nuanced form of bodily and behavioral insecurity. This insecurity can manifest itself in the form of the hyper-feminine behaviors that make up the feminine apologetic. Ultimately, athletes often feel a sense of internal fluidity and peace between their different identities, while also feeling the pressure to conform to a more acceptable form of femininity. This leaves these athletes in a constant state of tension in which they must negotiate gendered expectations with athletic responsibilities.

“Look Good, Feel Good, Play Good” emerged as an opportunistic title, considering the sad irony of its persistence among responses. Although it succinctly summarizes the nuanced pressures that many of the athletes described experiencing in women’s sports, it is its own type of cage. With the casual repetition of the phrase, the ideas have the potential to inconspicuously impact reality, leaving women athletes accidentally wielding words as tools of their own oppression. As it is spoken of, so it will be. The phrase prioritizes visual appearance as the first, and most important, of the steps towards playing well, essentially robbing athletes in women’s sports of their agency. By this logic, if they don’t look good, they can’t “feel good” or “play good.” More importantly, the syntax of the sentence conveys the message that feeling good and playing good are of less importance than the primary directive: look good. In order to change reality, it must first be interrogated. Who do these ideas serve? Who do they harm? What does the phrase really mean, when fully flushed out? Why do women continue to repeat it? How can these popular sayings be better leveraged for intentional messaging to girls and women? These questions open up a pathway to critical thought and reclaimed agency in popular discourse for athletes in women’s sports. Think well, feel well, speak well, and then play well. As it is spoken of, so it will be.

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